

Compressive Buckling of Graphite-Epoxy Composite Circular Cylindrical Shells

S. Kobayashi¹⁾, K. Koyama¹⁾, H. Seko¹⁾, K. Hirose²⁾

- 1) Department of Aeronautics, Faculty of Engineering, University of Tokyo, Hongo 7-chome, Bunkyo-ku, Tokyo 113, Japan
- 2) The Kamakura Works, Mitsubishi Electric Corporation, Kamimachiya, Kamakura, Kanagawa 247, Japan

ABSTRACT

Compressive buckling tests of four types of thin graphite-epoxy cylindrical shells made of prepreg sheets were carried out. The stacking sequences are $[20^\circ, -20^\circ, 90^\circ]$, $[0^\circ, 45^\circ, -45^\circ, 90^\circ]$, $[30^\circ, -30^\circ, -30^\circ, 30^\circ, 90^\circ, 90^\circ]$ and $[0^\circ, 60^\circ, -60^\circ, -60^\circ, 60^\circ, 0^\circ]$, where the top is inside, respectively. A theoretical analysis is attempted for the effect of prebuckling deformation on the buckling load. The calculated buckling loads of the test cylinders have disclosed the property that the prebuckling deformation raises the buckling load for the three of them. A good agreement is observed between theoretical and experimental results. At last the effects of the number of layers and the stacking sequence of lamination on the buckling load are disclosed by numerical analysis in comparison with the one of the corresponding orthotropic cylindrical shell. As a result, the optimum constitution of stacking sequence for the compressive buckling load is obtained for the 2-, 3-, 4-, 6-, and 8- layer cylinders, respectively.

INTRODUCTION

Graphite-epoxy composite cylindrical shells are now becoming important structural components in aerospace structures. However quite a few papers have been published for experimental studies on compressive buckling. Then an experimental study has been carried out at first. For comparison the theoretical buckling load has been calculated including the effect of prebuckling deformation. It is well known that the prebuckling deformation lowers the compressive buckling load of the isotropic cylindrical shells. This property was disclosed by Almroth (1) at first. After that, one of the authors performed similar analytical studies on isotropic conical shells (2) and on orthotropic cylindrical shells (3). Recently Jones (4) presented some analytical results on the effect of prebuckling deformation for cross-ply laminated circular cylindrical shells. At last the optimum stacking sequence of lamination for the compressive buckling load is studied.

EXPERIMENT

Buckling tests of four types of graphite-epoxy cylindrical shells made of prepreg sheets were carried out. The stacking sequence of lamination is shown in Table 1. The length and diameter of the cylindrical shell are 200 mm and 200 mm, respectively. Figure 1 shows the set-ups of experiment and illustrates

the fitting at the both ends of the shell. The angle of the fiber direction of prepreg sheets is illustrated in Fig.1. The test cylinders were prepared by Toray Industries Inc.. The boundary condition of both ends is regarded as 'perfectly clamped'. The end-shortening is applied by Instron testing machine as a method of loading.

The experimental buckling load $(P_{cr})_{exp}$ is shown in Table 1. n means the circumferential wave number. The load-end-shortening relation before buckling was linear in four experiments. The buckled deformation of the test cylinder No.2 is shown in Fig.2(A). In the cases of the test cylinders No.1 and No. 2, after the end-shortening was removed, they returned to a perfect cylinder, as the buckling deformation was almost elastic. On the other hand, in the cases of the test cylinders No.3 and No.4, failure occurred immediately after the buckling. In the case of the test cylinder No.3, a circumferential crack appeared as shown in Fig.2(B). In the case of the test cylinder No.4, some parts broke down as shown in Fig.2(C) and some broken pieces scattered. It was very dangerous experiment. As they happened instantaneously, we could not identify the value of n for the test cylinders No.3 and No.4.

The buckling load by the linear theory is the exact solution of Donnell type linear equation satisfying the perfectly clamped boundary condition. The method of analysis is the same with that of Cheng and Ho (5). The buckling load including the effect of prebuckling deformation was calculated by the author's new method of analysis explained in the next section. The values of elastic moduli used in the numerical analysis were calculated on the basis of the experimental and analytical data obtained in the author's previous studies (6,7). A good agreement is observed between experiment and theory including prebuckling deformation.

ANALYSIS

Method of analysis about the effect of prebuckling deformation on the buckling load is essentially the same as the one in the author's previous paper (2). However a new situation has appeared in the present test cylinders. The elastic moduli of the laminates are written as

$$\begin{pmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \\ M_x \\ M_y \\ M_{xy} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \underline{A_{xx}} & A_{xy} & \underline{A_{xs}} & B_{xx} & B_{xy} & \underline{B_{xs}} \\ A_{xy} & \underline{A_{yy}} & \underline{A_{ys}} & B_{xy} & B_{yy} & \underline{B_{ys}} \\ \underline{A_{xs}} & \underline{A_{ys}} & \underline{A_{ss}} & \underline{B_{xs}} & \underline{B_{ys}} & \underline{B_{ss}} \\ \underline{B_{xx}} & B_{xy} & \underline{B_{xs}} & \underline{D_{xx}} & D_{xy} & \underline{D_{xs}} \\ B_{xy} & B_{yy} & \underline{B_{ys}} & D_{xy} & \underline{D_{yy}} & \underline{D_{ys}} \\ \underline{B_{xs}} & \underline{B_{ys}} & \underline{B_{ss}} & \underline{D_{xs}} & \underline{D_{ys}} & \underline{D_{ss}} \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_{xo} \\ \epsilon_{yo} \\ \gamma_{xyo} \\ \kappa_x \\ \kappa_y \\ \kappa_{xy} \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where $[A_{ij}, B_{ij}, D_{ij}] = \sum_{m=1}^N \int_{t_{m-1}}^{t_m} t_{m-1} [1, z, z^2] E_{ij}^{(m)} dz$ (2)

The underlined terms were not zero generally in the test cylinders. In the author's paper on the orthotropic cylinder and Jones' paper on the cross-ply cylinder, these terms are zero. These terms make the analysis complicated.

The fundamental nonlinear equations of composite cylinders. i.e. the equation of equilibrium and the equation of compatibility, are expressed in terms of the deflection w and the stress function F , which is defined by $N_x = F,yy$, $N_y = F,xx$ and $N_{xy} = -F,xy$, as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & [C_{12}F,xxxx + (2C_{22} - C_{13})F,xxxy + (C_{11} + C_{22} - 2C_{33})F,xyyy + (2C_{31} - C_{23})F,xyyy \\ & + C_{21}F,yyyy] - [d_{11}w,xxxx + 2(d_{13} + d_{31})w,xxxy + (d_{12} + d_{21} + 4d_{33})w,xyyy \\ & + 2(d_{23} + d_{32})w,xyyy + d_{22}w,yyyy] - F,xx/R + F,yyw,xx + F,xxw,yy - 2F,xyw,xy = 0 \quad (3) \\ & [a_{22}F,xxxx - (a_{23} + a_{32})F,xxxy + (a_{12} + a_{21} + a_{33})F,xyyy - (a_{13} + a_{31})F,xyyy \\ & + a_{11}F,yyyy] + [b_{21}w,xxxx + (2b_{23} - b_{31})w,xxxy + (b_{11} + b_{22} - 2b_{33})w,xyyy + \\ & (2b_{13} - b_{32})w,xyyy + b_{12}w,yyyy] = w,xx/R + (w,xy)^2 - w,xxw,yy \quad (4) \end{aligned}$$

where $[a] = [A]^{-1}$, $[b] = [A]^{-1}[B]$, $[c] = [B][a]$, $[d] = [D] - [B][b]$ (5)

For the prebuckling deformation, the authors have taken the following two assumptions. The first is that the differentiation of deformation with respect

to y is zero. The second is that the distributions of N_x and N_{xy} at the loading edges are uniform. As the load is axial compression alone, we have a condition $\int_0^{2\pi} N_{xy} dy = 0$ at the loading edges. Then we get $N_{xy} = 0$ at the loading edges. Using the equation of equilibrium for in-plane stresses: i.e. $N_{x,x} + N_{xy,y} = 0$, we can derive the properties that $N_x = -N_0$ and $N_{xy} = 0$ for in-plane stresses. N_0 means the axial compressive load per unit length in the uniform distribution. Therefore we can express the stress function F_A for prebuckling deformation as

$$F_A = -N_0 y^2 / 2 + f_A(x) \quad (6)$$

In the present assumption a circumferential displacement $v_A(x)$ is allowable. Finally we can derive the equation of prebuckling deformation $w_A(x)$

$$(\bar{d}_1 + \bar{c}_{12} \bar{b}_2) w_A, \xi \xi \xi \xi + [\alpha - (\bar{c}_{12} + \bar{b}_2)] w_A, \xi \xi + w_A = -(a_2 / a_{22}) \alpha \quad (7)$$

where the following nondimensional symbols are used:

$$w_A = w_A / t, \quad \xi = x / \sqrt{Rt}, \quad \alpha = N_0 a_{22} R / t, \quad [\bar{b}] = [b] / t, \quad [\bar{c}] = [c] / t, \quad [\bar{d}] = a_{22} [d] / t^2 \quad (8)$$

The suffix A indicates the prebuckling deformation. The equation (7) is the same type with the one in previous paper (2). Then we can get the analytical solution easily.

The buckling load of unsymmetrical mode is obtained as a problem of bifurcation point from the prebuckling deformation. We express the displacements and the stress function in the following form:

$$w = w_A + w_B, \quad u = u_A + u_B, \quad v = v_A + v_B, \quad F = F_A + F_B \quad (9)$$

The quantities with suffix B are disturbances which are infinitesimally small. As we have terms having odd-time differentiations with respect to y in the equations (3) and (4), we must take the following type of expressions as a function of the circumferential coordinate:

$$w_B / t = w_{sn}(x) \sin n\theta + w_{cn}(x) \cos n\theta, \quad F_B / (t^2 / a_{22}) = f_{sn}(x) \sin n\theta + f_{cn}(x) \cos n\theta \quad (10)$$

Substituting the equations (9) and (10) into the equations (3) and (4), we get the following two equations of equilibrium and two equations of compatibility for quantities w_{sn} , w_{cn} , f_{sn} and f_{cn} :

$$\begin{aligned} & [\bar{c}_{12} f_{sn}, \xi \xi \xi \xi - (2\bar{c}_3 z - \bar{c}_{13}) \beta f_{cn}, \xi \xi \xi - (\bar{c}_{11} + \bar{c}_2 z - 2\bar{c}_{33}) \beta^2 f_{sn}, \xi \xi + (2\bar{c}_3 r - \bar{c}_{23}) \beta^3 f_{cn}, \xi \\ & + \bar{c}_2 \beta^4 f_{sn}] - [\bar{d}_1 w_{sn}, \xi \xi \xi \xi - 2(\bar{d}_{13} + \bar{d}_3) \beta w_{cn}, \xi \xi \xi - (\bar{d}_{12} + \bar{d}_2 + 4\bar{d}_{33}) \beta^2 w_{sn}, \xi \xi + 2(\bar{d}_2 z + \bar{d}_{32}) \\ & \times \beta^3 w_{cn}, \xi + \bar{d}_{22} \beta^4 w_{sn}] - f_{sn}, \xi \xi - w_A, \xi \xi \beta^2 f_{sn} - \alpha w_{sn}, \xi \xi - \beta^2 (w_A + \alpha \bar{a}_2 r - \bar{b}_2) w_A, \xi \xi w_{sn} = 0 \\ & [\bar{c}_{12} f_{cn}, \xi \xi \xi \xi + (2\bar{c}_3 z - \bar{c}_{13}) \beta f_{sn}, \xi \xi \xi - (\bar{c}_{11} + \bar{c}_2 z - 2\bar{c}_{33}) \beta^2 f_{cn}, \xi \xi - (2\bar{c}_3 r - \bar{c}_{23}) \beta^3 f_{sn}, \xi \\ & + \bar{c}_2 \beta^4 f_{cn}] - [\bar{d}_1 w_{cn}, \xi \xi \xi \xi + 2(\bar{d}_{13} + \bar{d}_3) \beta w_{sn}, \xi \xi \xi - (\bar{d}_{12} + \bar{d}_2 + 4\bar{d}_{33}) \beta^2 w_{cn}, \xi \xi \\ & - 2(\bar{d}_2 z + \bar{d}_{32}) \beta^3 w_{sn}, \xi + \bar{d}_{22} \beta^4 w_{cn}] - f_{cn}, \xi \xi - w_A, \xi \xi \beta^2 f_{cn} - \alpha w_{cn}, \xi \xi - \beta^2 (w_A + \bar{a}_2 \alpha - \bar{b}_2) w_A, \xi \xi \\ & \times w_{cn} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & [f_{sn}, \xi \xi \xi \xi + (\bar{a}_{23} + \bar{a}_{32}) \beta f_{cn}, \xi \xi \xi - (\bar{a}_{12} + \bar{a}_2 z + \bar{a}_{33}) \beta^2 f_{sn}, \xi \xi - (\bar{a}_{13} + \bar{a}_3) \beta^3 f_{cn}, \xi + \bar{a}_1 \beta^4 f_{sn}] \\ & + [\bar{b}_2 w_{sn}, \xi \xi \xi \xi - (2\bar{b}_2 z - \bar{b}_{33}) \beta w_{cn}, \xi \xi \xi - (\bar{b}_{11} + \bar{b}_2 z - 2\bar{b}_{33}) \beta^2 w_{sn}, \xi \xi + (2\bar{b}_1 z - \bar{b}_{32}) \beta^3 w_{cn}, \xi \\ & + \bar{b}_{12} \beta^4 w_{sn}] - (w_{sn}, \xi \xi + w_A, \xi \xi \beta^2 w_{sn}) = 0 \\ & [f_{cn}, \xi \xi \xi \xi - (\bar{a}_{23} + \bar{a}_{32}) \beta f_{sn}, \xi \xi \xi - (\bar{a}_{12} + \bar{a}_2 z + \bar{a}_{33}) \beta^2 f_{cn}, \xi \xi + (\bar{a}_{13} + \bar{a}_3) \beta^3 f_{sn}, \xi + \bar{a}_1 \beta^4 f_{cn}] \\ & + [\bar{b}_2 w_{cn}, \xi \xi \xi \xi + (2\bar{b}_2 z - \bar{b}_{33}) \beta w_{sn}, \xi \xi \xi - (\bar{b}_{11} + \bar{b}_2 z - 2\bar{b}_{33}) \beta^2 w_{cn}, \xi \xi - (2\bar{b}_1 z - \bar{b}_{32}) \beta^3 w_{sn}, \xi \\ & + \bar{b}_{12} \beta^4 w_{cn}] - (w_{cn}, \xi \xi + w_A, \xi \xi \beta^2 w_{cn}) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Now we take 'perfectly clamped' boundary condition:

$$w_{sn} = w_{cn} = 0, \quad w_{sn}, \xi = w_{cn}, \xi = 0, \quad v_{sn} = v_{cn} = 0, \quad u_{sn} = u_{cn} = 0 \quad (13)$$

The conditions $v_{sn} = v_{cn} = 0$ and $u_{sn} = u_{cn} = 0$ are expressed in terms of w_{sn} , w_{cn} , f_{sn}

between the ratio $(Pcr)_{pre}/(Pcr)_{lin}$ and the changing of θ is shown in Fig.4. $\theta=60^\circ$ corresponds to the test cylinder No.4. Figure 5 shows the change of the ratio $(Pcr)_{pre}/(Pcr)_{lin}$ as a function of volume fraction V_f in the condition that the fibers in all layers are in axial direction. $V_f=0$ corresponds to the isotropic epoxy cylinder. The result shows the stiffening in axial direction raises the ratio to more than 1.0 at a low volume fraction. Namely the results shown in Figs.4 and 5 connect the case of the isotropic cylinder and that of the test cylinder No.4. In the case of the test cylinder No.3, the prebuckling deformation lowers the buckling load and changes the mode to the unsymmetrical one, as the buckling mode in the linear theory is axi-symmetrical.

OPTIMUM STACKING SEQUENCE

As the second item, the optimum constitution of the stacking sequence of lamination of graphite-epoxy cylindrical shells has been studied under the condition to get the highest compressive buckling load. If we can consider that the laminates are composed of many numbers of layers of very thin prepreg sheets, the laminates are regarded as homogeneous in the thickness direction, namely orthotropic materials. The shells are composed of three types of layers of which fiber directions are 0° (axial layer), 90° (circumferential layer) and $\pm\theta$ (helical layer) with respect to the generatrix of the cylinder. Each thickness is written as t_a , t_c and t_h , respectively. The following symbols are used for the percentage of each layer:

$$\beta_a=t_a/t, \quad \beta_c=t_c/t, \quad \beta_h=t_h/t \quad (\rightarrow\beta_a+\beta_c+\beta_h=1) \quad (21)$$

where $t=t_a+t_c+t_h$ is the total thickness. In this type of orthotropic cylinder, we have the property that $B_{ij}=0$, $A_{xs}=A_{ys}=D_{xc}=D_{ys}=0$ in the elastic moduli of the equation (1) and the principal axes of the orthotropy are the axial and circumferential directions.

In the case of the boundary condition S2, i.e. $w=0$, $M_x=0$, $N_x=0$ and $v=0$, the exact solutions $\bar{N}(\alpha\alpha t)$ are easily obtained. Then if we regard the axial wave length λ_x as continuous, we derive the classical buckling stress in the axi-symmetrical mode

$$\sigma_{crs}=\sqrt{ExEy/[3(1-\nu_x\nu_y)]}(t/R) \quad (22)$$

from the calculation of $\partial\bar{N}/\partial\lambda_x^2=0$. For the check-board pattern mode, regarding the axial and circumferential wave lengths, λ_x and λ_y as continuous, we get the formula of classical buckling stress

$$\sigma_{cru}=Cu\sigma_{crs}, \quad Cu=\sqrt{[ExEy+2G_{xy}(1-\nu_x\nu_y)+Ex\nu_y]}/[\sqrt{ExEy+ExEy/(2G_{xy})}-Ex\nu_y] \quad (23)$$

from the calculation of $\partial\bar{N}/\partial[(\lambda_x/\lambda_y)^2]=0$ and $\partial\bar{N}/\partial(\lambda_x^2)=0$. The solutions of the type (22) and (23) were originally derived by Hayashi (8). The elastic moduli Ex etc. are expressed in terms of the elastic moduli EL etc. of the unidirectional composite and β_h, β_a and θ (9). In the present numerical example the following values are used in the condition of $V_f=65\%$ (7):

$$EL=1.50 \times 10^4 \text{ kgf/mm}^2, \quad ET=9.62 \times 10^2 \text{ kgf/mm}^2, \quad GLT=5.16 \times 10^2 \text{ kgf/mm}^2, \quad \nu_L=0.32$$

The buckling stress σ_{cr} is discussed with a coefficient f defined as

$$f=\sigma_{cr}R/t \quad \rightarrow \quad Pcr=2\pi t^2 f \quad (24)$$

because the value of f is independent of the dimensions R and t and is a function of EL etc., β_a , β_h and θ .

Figure 6(A) shows the results for $\beta_h=1.0$, namely angle-ply. The line with S shows the buckling load in the axi-symmetrical mode, and the line with U shows the one in the unsymmetrical mode in Fig.6. In the range where the value of C_u in the equation (23) is greater than 1.0, the equation (23) does not yield the smallest value of the unsymmetrical buckling load, because $\partial\bar{N}/\partial\lambda_x^2=0$ and $\partial\bar{N}/\partial\lambda_y^2=0$ are not the complete condition for the smallest value. The smallest buckling load in unsymmetrical mode is yielded by the circumferential wave number $n=2$ as shown by the broken line with U in Fig. 6(A), and is a little bit higher than the axi-symmetrical one. Figure 6(C) shows that, in the case of $\beta_h=0$, namely cross-ply, the maximum buckling load is given at the point of $\beta_a=\beta_c=0.5$ in the unsymmetrical buckling mode.

For the cases of the combination of angle-ply and cross-ply, the lowest

buckling load line is drawn with indication of the buckling mode by U or S as shown in Fig.6(B) as an example. In Fig.6(B), the largest buckling load is given at the point of intersection between the unsymmetrical buckling load line and the axisymmetrical one. In the cases of $\beta h=0, 0.1, 0.2,$ and 0.3 the axisymmetrical buckling load line does not cross the unsymmetrical buckling load line like as Fig.6(C). Namely, the unsymmetrical buckling load is lower for all angles of θ . The largest buckling load coefficient and the corresponding lamination for each value of βh are collected in Table 2. The table shows that the optimum lamination is not one but is found in the range of $\beta h=0.5\sim 0.8$ because three types of layers are taken. As a conclusion, the maximum value of f is about 3480 kgf/mm^2 .

However, in the case of thin shell of which number of layers is not so many, the homogeneous approximation in the thickness direction is not realized. Therefore the buckling load is lower than that of the corresponding homogeneous one, and the stacking sequence is important for the buckling load. The buckling load coefficient f is calculated for the cases of 2,3,4,6 and 8 layers, with the boundary condition S2. An energy method (10) where the strain energy is expressed as a function of the deflection w and the stress function F is used in the calculation. The buckling mode is assumed as $w=\bar{w}\sin(\pi x/\lambda_x)$ for the axisymmetrical mode and $w=\bar{w}\sin(\pi x/\lambda_x)\sin(\pi y/\lambda_y)$ for the unsymmetrical mode and F is obtained so as to satisfy the equation of compatibility. As an example of the results, the effect of stacking sequence on the buckling load is shown in Fig.7 taking the angle θ as the abscissa for three-layer one whose fiber directions are $0,+\theta$ and $-\theta$. The broken line shows the solution for the corresponding orthotropic cylinder. The optimum lamination in the range of this figure is $\theta=30^\circ$ on the line A. Figure 8 shows another example. The optimum lamination in the range of Fig.8 is given by $\theta=60^\circ$ on the line E.

The buckling load coefficient is calculated for all combinations of each type of lamination. The maximum value of f with the corresponding optimum stacking sequence for each type of lamination is collected in Table 3. The maximum value of f of the corresponding orthotropic cylinder in the same percentage of layers is also shown. The maximum value of f for each number of layers is underlined in Table 3. In the case of two-layer one the value of f for the optimum lamination is about 47% of the maximum value $f_{m0}=3480 \text{ kgf/mm}^2$ obtained for the orthotropic cylinder. The value of f_{\max} of the 6-layer one is very close to f_{m0} . The value of f_{\max} of the 8-layer one is a little bit lower than that of the 6-layer one. This property is due to the restriction on the percentage of the three types of layers.

Using the underlined values and taking the thickness of a prepreg sheet as $1/8\text{mm}$, we can get the Per-t relation as shown in Fig.9. The chain line corresponds to f_{m0} of the orthotropic cylinder. The buckling load of duralumin cylinder in the classical theory is drawn by the broken line for comparison under the condition of the same weight. Namely the abscissa t_{eff} is equal to $t \times (1.60/2.80)$. It is observed that in the case of two-layer one the buckling load is about the same as the one of the duralumin cylinder.

CONCLUSION

It is considered that the present theoretical and experimental studies yield the following conclusion.

- 1) Although the numerical example is limited for the test cylinders, the prebuckling deformation raises the buckling load for the cylinder whose buckling mode in the linear theory is unsymmetrical. For the cylinder whose buckling mode in the linear theory is axisymmetrical, the prebuckling deformation lowers the buckling load and changes the mode to unsymmetrical one.
- 2) Better agreement is obtained between theoretical and experimental results compared with that of the isotropic cylinder.
- 3) The stacking sequence of lamination yields a great influence on the buckling load in the case where the number of layers is not many. The optimum stacking sequence and the corresponding buckling load coefficient are found for the 2-, 3-, 4-, 6- and 8- layer cylinders, respectively. In the case of the 2-layer one the optimum lamination yields about the same buckling load with that of a duralumin cylinder under the condition of the same weight. If the number of layers is greater than six, the buckling load coefficient for the optimum stacking sequence is close to the optimum value of orthotropic cylinders.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors wish to express their gratitude to Messrs. M. Fujiwara and T. Norita, Pioneering Research and Development Laboratories of TORAY Industries Inc., for the preparation of the test specimens.

REFERENCES

- 1) Almroth, B.O., "Influence of Edge Conditions on the Stability of Axially Compressed Cylindrical Shells", NASA CR-161, 1965.
- 2) Kobayashi, S., "The Influence of Prebuckling Deformation on the Buckling Load of Truncated Conical Shells under Axial Compression", NASA CR-707, 1967/Jan.
- 3) Kobayashi, S., "The Influence of Prebuckling Deformation on the Buckling Load of Orthotropic Cylindrical Shells under Axial Compression", Trans. Japan Soc. Aeronaut. and Space Sci. Vol.11, No.19. 1968. P.60.
- 4) Jones, R.M. and Hennemann, J.C.F., "Effect of Prebuckling Deformations on Buckling of Laminated Composite Circular Cylindrical Shells", AIAA Jour., Vol.18, 1980, P.110.
- 5) Cheng, S. and Ho, B.P.C., "Stability of Heterogeneous Anisotropic Cylindrical Shells under Combined Loading", AIAA Jour., Vol.1, 1963, P.892.
- 6) Kobayashi, S. and Ishikawa, T., "Elastic Properties of Unidirectional Fiber-Reinforced Composites", Fukugo Zairyo Kenkyu, Vol.3, No.3, 1974, P.12.
- 7) Ishikawa, T., Koyama, K. and Kobayashi, S., "Elastic Moduli of Carbon-Epoxy Composites and Carbon Fibers", Jour. Composite Materials, Vol.11, 1977/July, P.249.
- 8) Hayashi, T., "On the Elastic Instability of Orthogonal Anisotropic Cylindrical Shells, Especially the Buckling Load due to Compression, Bending and Torsion", Jour. Soc. Naval Arch. Japan, No.81, 1949, P.85.
- 9) Ishikawa, T., Taki, T., and Kobayashi, S., "Thermal Residual Stresses and Failure Strengths of Filament Wound CFRP Materials", Jour. Japan Soc. Aeronaut. and Space Sci., Vol.27, 1979, P.370.
- 10) Khot, N.S., "Buckling and Postbuckling Behavior of Composite Cylindrical Shells under Axial Compression", AIAA Jour. Vol.8, 1970, P.229.

Table 1 Comparison between Experimental and Theoretical Buckling Loads

No.	Lamination (inner → outer)	Thickness (mm)	V _f (%)	Experiment P _{cr exp} (kgf)	Linear Theory P _{cr lin} (kgf)	Prebuckling P _{cr pre} (kgf)	P _{cr exp} / P _{cr lin}	P _{cr exp} / P _{cr pre}	P _{cr pre} / P _{cr lin}
1	+20°, -20°, 90°	0.420	56.4	1353 (n=10)	1440 (n=15)	1447 (n=14)	0.940	0.916	1.026
2	0°, +45°, -45°, 90°	0.578	58.4	2788 (n= 8)	2869 (n=12)	3022 (n=14)	0.972	0.923	1.053
3	+30°; -30°; -30°; +30°; 90°; 90°	0.899	57.6	9013 (n= ?)	11498 (n= 0)	11112 (n= 4)	0.784	0.811	0.966
4	0°, +60°; -60°; -60°; +60°; 0°	1.017	52.8	10013 (n= ?)	10765 (n= 8)	12139 (n=10)	0.930	0.825	1.128

Table 2 Maximum value of f accompanied with optimum (θ, β_a) for each value of β_h

β _h	0	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	1.0
f $\frac{kgf}{mm^2}$	1690	2170	2570	2900	3210	3465	3470	3480	3350	2920	2090
θ deg	/	45	45	45	45	45	32 58	29 61	25 65	21 69	15 75
β _a	0.5	0.4 0.5	0.4	0.3 0.4	0.3	0.2 0.3	0 0.4	0 0.3	0 0.2	0 0.1	0

Table 3 f_{max} with optimum stacking sequence for each type of lamination

No. of Layers	Type of Lamination	No. of Combination	Optimum Stacking Sequence	f_{max} 10^3 $\frac{kgf}{mm^2}$	$f_{max}/10^3$ of Orthotropic One
2	$0^\circ-1, 90^\circ-1$ $\theta^\circ-1, -\theta^\circ-1$	2	$(0^\circ, 90^\circ), (90^\circ, 0^\circ)$	1.18	1.69
		1	$(15^\circ, -15^\circ), (75^\circ, -75^\circ)$	<u>1.62</u>	$2.09 (\theta=15^\circ)$ $(\theta=75^\circ)$
3	$0^\circ-1, \theta^\circ-1, -\theta^\circ-1$ $90^\circ-1, \theta^\circ-1, -\theta^\circ-1$	3	$(0^\circ, 30^\circ, -30^\circ)$	<u>2.14</u>	$3.48 (\theta=60^\circ)$
		3	$(90^\circ, 60^\circ, -60^\circ)$	2.13	$3.48 (\theta=30^\circ)$
4	$\theta^\circ-2, -\theta^\circ-2$ $0^\circ-2, \theta^\circ-1, -\theta^\circ-1$ $90^\circ-2, \theta^\circ-1, -\theta^\circ-1$ $0^\circ-1, 90^\circ-1, \theta^\circ-1, -\theta^\circ-1$	2	$\left. \begin{array}{l} (15^\circ, -15^\circ, -15^\circ, 15^\circ) \\ (75^\circ, -75^\circ, -75^\circ, 75^\circ) \end{array} \right\}$	2.09	$2.09 (\theta=15^\circ)$ $(\theta=75^\circ)$
		6	$(60^\circ, 0^\circ, -60^\circ, 0^\circ)$	2.50	$3.28 (\theta=53^\circ)$
		6	$(30^\circ, 90^\circ, -30^\circ, 90^\circ)$	2.46	$3.28 (\theta=37^\circ)$
		12	$\left. \begin{array}{l} (0^\circ, 90^\circ, 45^\circ, -45^\circ) \\ (90^\circ, 0^\circ, 45^\circ, -45^\circ) \end{array} \right\}$	2.42	$3.48 (\theta=48^\circ)$
6	$0^\circ-1, \theta^\circ-1, -\theta^\circ-1, Sym$ $90^\circ-1, \theta^\circ-1, -\theta^\circ-1, Sym$ $0^\circ-2, \theta^\circ-1, HS$ $90^\circ-2, \theta^\circ-1, HS$ $0^\circ-1, 90^\circ-1, \theta^\circ-1, HS$	3	$(60^\circ, 0^\circ, -60^\circ, Sym)$	3.21	$3.48 (\theta=60^\circ)$
		3	$(30^\circ, 90^\circ, -30^\circ, Sym)$	<u>3.37</u>	$3.48 (\theta=30^\circ)$
		3	$(0^\circ, 55^\circ, 0^\circ, -55^\circ, 0^\circ)$	2.20	$2.70 (\theta=50^\circ)$
		3	$(90^\circ, 35^\circ, 90^\circ, 90^\circ, -35^\circ, 90^\circ)$	2.19	$2.70 (\theta=40^\circ)$
		6	$\left. \begin{array}{l} (0^\circ, 90^\circ, 45^\circ, -45^\circ, 90^\circ, 0^\circ) \\ (90^\circ, 0^\circ, 45^\circ, -45^\circ, 0^\circ, 90^\circ) \\ (30^\circ, 0^\circ, 90^\circ, 90^\circ, 0^\circ, -30^\circ) \\ (60^\circ, 90^\circ, 0^\circ, 0^\circ, 90^\circ, -60^\circ) \end{array} \right\}$	2.56	$3.01 (\theta=45^\circ)$
8	$0^\circ-2, \theta^\circ-1, -\theta^\circ-1, Sym$ $90^\circ-2, \theta^\circ-1, -\theta^\circ-1, Sym$ $0^\circ-1, 90^\circ-1, \theta^\circ-1, -\theta^\circ-1, Sym$	6	$(55^\circ, 0^\circ, 0^\circ, -55^\circ, Sym)$	3.20	$3.27 (\theta=53^\circ)$
		6	$(35^\circ, 90^\circ, 90^\circ, -35^\circ, Sym)$	3.28	$3.27 (\theta=37^\circ)$
		12	$(55^\circ, 0^\circ, -55^\circ, 90^\circ, Sym)$	<u>3.32</u>	$3.48 (\theta=45^\circ)$

Sym means to be symmetrical with respect to the middle surface.

HS means to be symmetrical with respect to the middle surface except for changing $+\theta$ to $-\theta$.

(A) No.2

(B) No.3

(C) No.4

Fig.2 Photograph of Buckled Deformation or Failure

Fig.1 Test Set-up

Fig.3 Coordinates and Symbols

Fig.4 $(P_{cr})_{pre} / (P_{cr})_{lin}$ versus θ for lamination $(0^\circ, +\theta^\circ, -\theta^\circ, -\theta^\circ, +\theta^\circ, 0^\circ)$ and $V_f = 55\%$

Fig.5 $(P_{cr})_{pre} / (P_{cr})_{lin}$ versus V_f for unidirectional cylinder

Fig.9 Effect of layers on $(P_{cr})_{max}$

Fig.6 Buckling load coefficient f of unsymmetrical and axi-symmetrical modes

Fig.7 f versus θ for type of lamination $(0^\circ-1,+ \theta^\circ-1,- \theta^\circ-1)$

Fig.8 f versus θ for type of lamination $(0^\circ-2,+ \theta^\circ-1,- \theta^\circ-1)$